

Session 2E: Understanding co-creation of fused data

From Co-Creation to Multi-Destination Impact: Who Creates, Who Benefits

Host – Symposium Sponsor

International Partners

National Supporters

2E: Understanding co-creation of fused data

Angela-Maria Despotopoulou

Angela-Maria is a software and systems engineer, currently involved in EU-funded R&D projects as an employee of Frontier Innovations.

As a technical coordinator of the EvoRoads project, she bridges system architecture with real-world mobility. With deep expertise in distributed systems and software engineering, she orchestrates the integration of AI, sensors, and digital twins across European pilots -delivering data-driven safety innovations that scale from codebase to curbside.

From Co-Creation to Multi-Destination Impact: Who Creates, Who Benefits

Angela-Maria Despotopoulou

Frontier Innovations

Co-Creation: What It Really Means (1/2)

Co-Creation: What It Really Means (1/2)

Co-Creation: What It Really Means (1/2)

Co-Creation: What It Really Means (2/2)

If I give you
my data, I
lose
something.

Co-Creation: What It Really Means (2/2)

If I give you
my data, I
lose
something.

Data isn't
given away;
it is
leveraged.

Data as Currency

Currency circulates. It retains value. It gains value through exchange.

But it also does something else:

- It creates a new safety feature the OEM can **monetize**.
- It gives the city the intelligence to reduce accidents - and apply for smart infrastructure funding.
- It lets insurers model risk more accurately - creating new pricing models.

Platform Network Effects

Dozens of cities. Thousands of vehicles. Millions of events.

This is where platform **network effects** kick in.

So, when people ask, "Why share?"

The answer is: "Because the value of your data goes up when others add theirs."

Who Monetises, Who Capitalises?

Not everyone wants to “monetize.”
But *everyone* wants value.

Private Sector (OEMs, Startups)	Public Sector (Cities, Road Agencies)
Revenue via services, APIs	Efficiency, impact, credibility
Market edge & differentiation	Grant access, public trust
Insurance innovation	Reduced liability, smarter policy

Same data. Different dividends.

The Road User's Perspective

For them, this isn't about monetization.

It's about **trust** and **tangible benefit**.

They're not part of the data-sharing contract.

But they're the reason **it exists**.

A Quick Glimpse of Active Projects

Mobility
Data Space

Data Sharing Community

A collaborative platform that enables the secure exchange and integration of mobility data across various stakeholders to improve transportation services and foster innovation in the mobility sector.

mobility-dataspace.eu

An initiative aimed at implementing and scaling the European Mobility Data Space (EMDS) by developing technical standards, infrastructure, and governance models for secure and interoperable mobility data sharing across Europe.

deployemds.eu

A European data-sharing platform that provides access to a comprehensive collection of road safety data, enabling stakeholders to analyse trends, monitor performance, and develop evidence-based safety measures.

dataforroadsafety.eu

A European initiative that facilitates the exchange of real-time traffic and road network data between public authorities and service providers to improve traffic management and navigation services.

tn-its.eu

EVORODADS in Action

Funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra
Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Romania

Latvia

Take Away

We're at a tipping point.

What we need is a **mindset shift**.

From:

"My data is my property" → to "My data can generate shared value."

"Collaboration is loss of control" → to "Collaboration is strategic leverage."

• In short:

- Don't hoard the data.
- Shape the ecosystem.

THANK YOU!

Angela-Maria Despotopoulou
angelina.despotopoulou@frontier-innovations.com

Host – Symposium Sponsor

International Partners

National Supporters

